

Triterpenoids. XXXIV

The Structure and Stereochemistry of Entagenic Acid

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The isolation of a new triterpene acid sapogenin, entagenic acid, from the kernel of the seed of *Entada phaseoloides* Merrill (Syn. *E. scandens*, *E. pursaetha*) was reported by Barua¹ who proposed two alternative structures. 3, 15, 16-trihydroxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid and 3, 21, 22-trihydroxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid for it. Later the second alternative structure was preferred for entagenic acid and its stereochemistry was represented as (I)^{2,3}. Further studies, which are described in this paper, however, show that entagenic acid is 3 β , 15 α , 16 α -trihydroxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid (IIa).

Entagenic acid on heating with pyridine and acetic anhydride on steam bath furnished a product which showed two distinct major spots in t.l.c. and one of these spots corresponded to that of the amorphous triacetyl entagenic acid reported earlier (*loc. cit.*). Treatment of the above acetate mixture with diazomethane furnished triacetyl methyl entagenate, C₃₇H₅₆O₈, m.p. 203–205° (IIc) and diacetyl methyl entagenate, C₃₅H₅₄O₇, m.p. 200° (softens at 175°) (IIId), both in good yields. Methyl entagenate (IIb) on treatment with pyridine and acetic anhydride at 0° furnished mainly diacetyl methyl entagenate (IIId) and 3-acetyl methyl entagenate², C₃₅H₅₂O₆, m.p. 262–65° (IIe) and only trace of triacetyl methyl entagenate (IIc). The above experiment clearly showed that one of the hydroxyl groups of the α -glycol system in entagenic acid is hindered.

The α -glycol system in entagenic acid was shown earlier to be *cis* as it easily formed an acetonide and consumed lead tetraacetate at a fast rate. Therefore, if the α -glycol system is located in ring E, the configurations of these two hydroxyl groups should be either 21 β , 22 β or 21 α , 22 α . Entagenic acid did not form any 28 \rightarrow 21 lactone like machaerinic acid (*loc. cit.*) which contains a 21 β hydroxyl group and hence the configuration of the α -glycol system should be 21 α , 22 α if it is located in ring E. But the 21 α and 22 α hydroxyl groups both undergo acetylation with pyridine and acetic anhydride under mild conditions⁴. Thus the hindrance of one of the hydroxyl groups in entagenic acid towards acetylation cannot be explained if the α -glycol system is located at C-21 and C-22 positions. Therefore the alternative positions (C-15 and C-16) for the α -glycol system had to be considered. If the α -glycol system is located in ring D then there are two possible configurations for the two

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hydroxyl groups, either 15β , 16β or 15α , 16α . 15β -hydroxyl is known to undergo easy lactonization with 28-carboxyl group (cf. dumortierigenin⁵ and proceragenin⁶) but entagenic acid did not form a 28 \rightarrow 15 lactone. Therefore if the α -glycol system is in ring D, then the configurations of these two hydroxyl groups should be 15α (equatorial) and 16α (axial). 16α -hydroxyl group in an oleanene skeleton is known to be hindered (cf. echinoecystic acid⁷ and barringtogenol C⁸) and this explains the hindrance of one of the hydroxyl groups of the α -glycol system in entagenic acid. The hydroxyl group at C-3 in entagenic acid was previously shown to β (equatorial). On the basis of the above discussions entagenic acid should be 3β , 15α , 16α -trihydroxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid (IIa).

- a, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = H$
 b, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H, R_4 = CH_3$
 c, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = COCH_3, R_4 = CH_3$
 d, $R_1 = R_2 = COCH_3, R_3 = H, R_4 = CH_3$
 e, $R_1 = COCH_3, R_2 = R_3 = H, R_4 = CH_3$
 f, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = COCH_3, R_4 = H$

The above conclusion was further corroborated by the facts presented below.

The mass spectrum of diacetyl methyl entagenate showed the molecular ion peak at m/e 586. The diacetyl methyl entagenate (IIId) is considered to be a 3,15-diacetate as preferential acetylation of the 15α (equatorial) hydroxyl group rather than the 16α (axial) hydroxyl group is expected. That it was so was evident from its N.M.R. spectrum ($CDCl_3$, 60 Mc). The two acetoxy groups ($-O.CO.CH_3$) appeared as sharp singlet at 2.03 (3H) and 2.07 (3H) δ . A three proton singlet at 3.68 δ was due to the 28-carbomethoxyl group ($-COOCH_3$). The C-12 vinyl proton appeared as a broad multiplet at 5.5 δ . Examination of the chemical shift of the carbonyl protons revealed that the proton ($H-\overset{\text{I}}{\underset{|}{C}}-O.CO.CH_3$)

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6. S. Roy and A. Roy, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1966, 5743.
7. J. Simonsen and W. C. J. Ross, "The Terpenes", (Cambridge University Press), 1957, Vol. V, 157.
8. A. K. Barua and P. Chakrabarti, *Tetrahedron*, 1965, **21**, 381.

corresponding to the acetylated hydroxyl group of the α -glycol system appeared at 5.15 δ (d , $J = 4$ c.p.s.) while that corresponding to the unacetylated hydroxyl ($H-\overset{|}{C}-OH$) appeared at 4.44 δ (d , $J = 4$ c.p.s.) which was partly overlapped by the signal at 4.48 δ (1H, m) due to the 3 α -proton ($H-\overset{|}{C}-O.CO.CH_3$). If the diacetate was a 3, 16-diacetyl derivative, then the signal for the 16 β -H ($H-\overset{|}{C}.COCH_3$) would have appeared further downfield than 5.69 δ (observed for 16 β -H in case of diacetyl methyl echinocystate) because presence of vicinal hydroxyl group at C-15 would cause further downfield shift of the signal. So the diacetate must be a 3, 15-diacetate (II*d*). This was further supported by the N.M.R. spectral studies of triacetyl entagenic acid (II*f*). The N.M.R. spectrum ($CDCl_3$, 60 Mc) of (II*f*) showed the signal at the expected low field (5.81 δ , 1H, d , $J = 4$ c.p.s.) for the 16 β -proton and at 5.3 δ (1H, d , $J = 4$ c.p.s.) for the 15 β -proton. Besides these, there were three sharp singlets at 1.92 (3H), 2.01 (3H) and 2.1 (3H) δ for three acetoxy groups ($-O.CO.CH_3$), a triplet 4.52 δ (1H, $J = 8$ c.p.s.) for the 3 α -proton and a broad multiplet at 5.5 δ (1H) for the C-12 vinyl proton.

III

$a, R = H$

$b, R = COCH_3$

Lithium aluminium hydride reduction of methyl entagenate furnished a tetrol, $C_{30}H_{50}O_4$, m.p. 254–56°, (III*a*) and this on heating with acetic anhydride and pyridine on steam bath furnished a mixture of acetates from which tetrol tetra-acetate (III*b*), $C_{38}H_{58}O_8$, m.p. 123–27°, was isolated in pure state by column chromatography. The N.M.R. spectrum ($CDCl_3$, 60 Mc) of tetrol tetra-acetate was in good agreement with its proposed structure (III*b*). The signals assignable to 23-, 24- (s, 6H, 0.87 δ), 25-, 29- (S, 6H, 0.93 δ) and 30- (S, 3H, 0.97 δ) methyl groups ($-\overset{|}{C}-CH_3$) appeared at the region as observed in case of 3 β -acetoxy compounds of the Δ^{12} -oleanene series⁹ but those for the 26- (S, 3H, 1.0 δ) and 27- (S, 3H, 1.4 δ) methyl groups appeared at lower field due to the vicinity of the acetoxy groups at C-15 and C-16 positions. Four acetoxy groups ($-O.CO.CH_3$) appeared as sharp singlets at 1.93 (3H), 2.04 (3H) and 2.13 (6H) δ . The methylene protons of the 28-primary acetoxy group ($-CH_2.O.CO.CH_3$) appeared as AB pattern centred at 3.64 (d , $J = 11.5$ c.p.s.) and

4.09 (d , $J = 11.5$ c.p.s.) δ . The 3α - (axial) proton ($H-\overset{|}{\underset{|}{C}}-O.CO.CH_3$) appeared as a broad triplet at 4.5 δ . The two carbonyl protons (15β -H and 16β -H) of the vicinal acetoxy groups appeared as an AB type centred at 5.24 (d , $J = 4$ c.p.s.) and 5.45 (d , $J = 4$ c.p.s.) δ respectively. The low coupling constant (4 c.p.s.) indicated *cis* relationship between the above two protons which necessitates *cis*-orientation for the α -glycol system in (IIIb) and consequently in entagenic acid. The C-12 vinyl proton appeared as a broad multiplet at 5.49 δ .

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